

STUDIES ON THE SOLUBILITY AND LIGHT-FASTNESS OF AZO DYES. PART I

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The solubility of twelve azo dyes of benzene-azophenol series has been determined in benzene, petroleum ether and groundnut oil. The stability of these dyes towards sunlight has also been studied with the help of a photoelectric colorimeter.

As the oil-soluble dyes have great importance in printing, colouring of plastics, vegetable product, fats, waxes and gasoline, it was considered worthwhile to study the solubility of azo dyes in oil and organic solvents like benzene and petroleum ether. A survey of the literature reveals that very little work has been done in this field. In the present work, the effect of different groups like $-Cl$, $-NO_2$, $-CH_3$, $-OCH_3$ and $-HSO_3$, in different positions of the dye molecule on the solubility and stability towards light has been studied. It may be mentioned that the solubility and stability of dyes in oil proper has so far only been determined by Anon (*Farben Ztg.*, 1914, 19, 648) and that too, qualitatively. In all other cases, wherever oil solubility has been mentioned, either kerosine oil or liquid paraffin has been used. For determining the solubility of these dyes in oil, colorimetric method has been employed, since ordinary methods of solubility determination are not applicable.

The problem of the fastness of dyestuffs to sunlight has engaged the attention of chemists since the early days and various methods have been suggested by different workers from time to time (Knetch, *J. Soc. Dyers & Col.*, 1905, 21, 3, 154; Bancroft, *Orig. Com. 8th. Inter. Congr. Appl. Chem.*, 20, 91; Robson, *J. Soc. Dyers & Col.*, 1918, 34, 185; Haley, *ibid.*, 1918, 34, 201; Robinson *et al.*, *Am. Dyestuff Rep.*, 1923, 11, 384), but they had to be given up as they were either of theoretical importance or gave only approximate results. Moreover, the light-fastness has so far only been tested after their application on fabrics where the constitution of the fabric is known to play an important role (Gebhard, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1913, 37, 765; Busley, *Text. Col.*, 44, 367), and as such the absolute fastness of these dyes has so far not been measured.

Light-fastness of azo dyes was studied for the first time by Watson, Sarkar and Dutta (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1911, 30, 6) utilising Knetch's process for this purpose. This method did not give accurate results as had been acknowledged by the authors. Besides, they did not take full precautions against the factors that influence the light-fastness, as suggested by Rose (*Proc. Am. Text. & Col.*, 1926, 68) and further, their study was restricted to $-HSO_3$, $-COOH$, $-OH$ and $-NO_2$ groups only.

With these facts in view, a method has been developed by the present authors in which the absolute fastness of the dye can be measured accurately

in solution. The fading rate has been measured here with the help of a photo-electric colorimeter (Klett-Summerson) as the solutions were found to obey Beer's law within a wide range when proper filters were used.

EXPERIMENTAL

In these investigations twelve derivatives of benzene-azophenol were prepared by coupling phenol with appropriate diazonium salts in alkaline medium. In this way azo dyes with $-Cl$, $-NO_2$, $-CH_3$, $-OCH_3$ and $-HSO_3$ groups in different positions were obtained. Groundnut oil was chosen for its low viscosity and melting point for determining oil solubility. Two organic solvents viz., anhydrous benzene and petroleum ether (b. p. $60^\circ-70^\circ$) were also used for this purpose. The light-fastness of these dyes was tested in groundnut oil solutions as this solvent had no protecting effect which was observed in benzene and alcoholic solutions.

Solubility in Oil.—Saturated solutions of the dyes were prepared by shaking a mixture of an excess of the dye and groundnut oil, in sealed glass tubes, in a mechanical shaker for six hours at a constant temperature (40°) and subsequently filtering the solutions. Two standard solutions of the dye having different concentrations were prepared in benzene. Measured volumes of these standard solutions were added to known quantities of the oil. The saturated solution in oil in its turn was diluted with proportionate quantity of benzene. The colour intensity of the saturated solution was then compared with the standard solutions by means of the photo-electric colorimeter, using throughout the light of the same wave-length. The solubility was then calculated by the formula :

$$\text{Conc. of unknown (dye)} = \frac{\text{Conc. of known}}{\text{Reading of known}} \times \text{reading of unknown.}$$

Solubility in Benzene and Petroleum Ether.—Saturated solutions in benzene and petroleum ether were prepared as described in the case of oil except for the process of filtration. Since both the solvents were very volatile, the saturated solutions were carefully transferred by special pipettes, having cotton plugs, into specially designed doubly stoppered glass bottles. The solvents were subsequently evaporated in an air-bath (110°).

Fastness to Light.—About 0.1% solutions of the dyes were prepared in oil and were exposed to sunlight in sealed glass tubes of equal thickness and diameter to avoid humidity and temperature variations. Strengths of these solutions, before and after the exposure, were accurately determined with the help of the photo-electric colorimeter. The solutions were exposed to the sunlight in the month of June. A preliminary investigation after twelve days' exposure showed a general fading in different dyes. The results obtained are shown in Table II.

TABLE I
Solubility of the dyes.

Sr. No.	Dye.	M. p.	Solubility (100g.) in		
			Benzene at 30°.	Petrol ether at 30°.	ground-nut oil at 40°.
1.	4-Hydroxyazo-benzene	152°	(a) 1.647 (b) 1.628	(a) 0.138 (b) 0.142	(a) 4.517 (b) 4.526
2.	Anisol-(2-azo-4)-phenol	146°	(a) 1.102 (b) 1.103	(a) 0.139 (b) 0.140	(a) 2.262 (b) 2.300
3.	Anisol-(4-azo-4)-phenol	142°	(a) 2.09 (b) 2.08	(a) 0.0844 (b) 0.0864	(a) 3.344 (b) 3.372
4.	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzene-(1-azo-4)-phenol	85°	(a) 15.14 (b) 15.09	(a) 0.65 (b) 0.67	(a) 4.513 (b) 4.501
5.	<i>μ</i> -Chlorobenzene-(1-azo-4)-phenol	157°	(a) 3.527 (b) 3.531	(a) 0.204 (b) 0.208	(a) 4.365 (b) 4.386
6.	<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzene-(1-azo-4)-phenol	135°	(a) 6.404 (b) 6.370	(a) 0.314 (b) 0.306	(a) 6.243 (b) 6.182
7.	4- <i>p</i> -Toluolazo-phenol	151°	(a) 2.989 (b) 3.010	(a) 0.167 (b) 0.164	(a) 5.581 (b) 5.604
8.	4- <i>o</i> -Toluolazo-phenol	116°	(a) 21.90 (b) 21.80	(a) 1.97 (b) 2.00	(a) 5.884 (b) 5.843
9.	4- <i>m</i> -Toluolazo-phenol	137° (144°)	(a) 3.08 (b) 3.12	(a) 0.46 (b) 0.47	(a) 9.941 (b) 9.956
10.	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzene-(1-azo-4)-phenol	213°	(a) 0.330 (b) 0.329	(a) 0.00346 (b) 0.00639	(a) 0.775 (b) 0.786
11.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzene-(1-azo-4)-phenol	162°	(a) 7.16 (b) 7.20	(a) 0.00637 (b) 0.00639	(a) 1.135 (b) 1.160
12.	<i>p</i> -Sulphonylbenzene-(1-azo-4)-phenol	Does not melt.	(a) Insoluble	Insoluble	Insoluble

TABLE II
Fastness to light.

Sr. No.	Dye.	Initial eading.	Conc.	Col. reading after exposure.	Fading.
1.	4-Hydroxyazobenzene	27	0.9760%	20	25.9%
2.	Anisol-(2-azo-4)-phenol	79	0.1437	71	10.09
3.	Anisol-(4-azo-4)-phenol	74	0.1413	65	12.1
4.	<i>o</i> -Chlorobenzene-(1-azo-4)-phenol	13	0.0968	8	30.7
5.	<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzene-(1-azo-4)-phenol	40	0.1393	33	17.5
6.	4- <i>p</i> -Toluolazo-phenol	43	0.1363	38	11.12
7.	4- <i>o</i> -Toluolazo-phenol	35	0.1239	33	5.75
8.	4- <i>m</i> -Toluolazo-phenol	45	0.1377	43	6.68
9.	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzene-(1-azo-4)-phenol	137	0.1932	105	23.3
10.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzene-(1-azo-4)-phenol	74	0.1523	68	8.21

C O N C L U S I O N

As a result of these investigations a few inferences have been drawn which are given below :—

Solutions of these azo dyes on dilution obey Beer's law.

Substitution of $-CH_3$ and $-Cl$ groups in the amino part of the dye molecule increases the solubility, whereas substitution by $-NO_2$ and $-HSO_3$ groups decreases it.

In accordance with Mortimer's equation (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 45 633)

$$\text{Log } N = \frac{fL}{4.57} \left(\frac{1}{T_m} - \frac{1}{T} \right)$$

it has been found that the solubility of these dyes depends upon the melting point, viz., lower the melting point, higher the solubility and *vice versa*. In the case of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-isomers of a compound, the internal pressure, f , of the solvent, the latent heat of fusion, L , of the solute being constant quantities (cf. Glasstone, "Recent Advances in General Chemistry" and International Critical Tables) and the temperature, T being the same in each case, it is evident from the above equation that the solubility N is inversely proportional to the melting point T_m .

The above relationship holds good in the case of benzene and petroleum ether but not in the case of oil, which is a mixture of glycerides and not an ideal solvent. However, *m*-substituted dyes appear to be most soluble in oil as compared to *ortho* and *para* ones.

Table II shows that dye No. 4 having a $-Cl$ group in *ortho* position is most fugitive (30.7%) and dye No. 7, having a $-CH_3$ group in *ortho* position, is the least (5.75%).

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